

Durability behaviors of calcined kaolin clay-based geopolymer concrete containing different calcium compounds and cured in ambient sub-Saharan climate

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ABSTRACT

The addition of calcium-rich materials to geopolymers enables satisfactory mechanical performance to be achieved when curing takes place at ambient temperature. However, these calcium-rich products could influence the durability of these materials. This study assesses the effect of different calcium-rich additions on the durability of metakaolin (MK) based geopolymer concrete activated by NaOH solution 12 M and cured in ambient conditions of sub-Saharan climate (around 30°C). The MK was partially substituted by different types of calcium-rich additions, namely calcium carbide residue (CCR), quick lime (QLM), slaked lime (SLM), and ordinary Portland cement (OPC). After curing at room temperature at 30°C for 90 days, the concretes were subjected to various tests to assess their durability, namely water-accessible porosity; capillary absorption; wetting-drying and resistance to 0.5 % sulfuric and 1 % hydrochloric acid attack. The results indicate that the addition of calcium-rich products has various effects on concretes' durability. Its impact is negligible on the water-accessible porosity of concretes which remains stable at around 14.5 %, while it improves their capacity to absorb water by capillary action by reducing their sorptivity by more than 70 %. However, acid attack increasingly affects concretes as the calcium-rich product content increases. Quicklime shows the best overall durability performance, and in the acid attack test, QLM-containing concretes are the only ones to retain a compressive strengths exceeding 20 MPa after 28 days in acidic environment. Sulfuric acid is more aggressive to geopolymer concretes than hydrochloric acid. Wetting-drying cycles lead to additional porosity in the concretes as ultrasonic pulse velocities are reduced by more than 9 %, without any major detriment to compressive strength performance. However, flexural strength exhibited a decrease (between – 5 % and – 49 %) after wetting-drying cycles when CCR, SLM or QLM are used. Overall, the acid resistance of geopolymer concretes is influenced by their microstructure, particularly the presence of portlandite-like phases: concretes containing calcium-rich product with a higher propensity to form portlandite are more susceptible to acidic attack especially in sulfuric acid environment.

Keywords:

Ambient curing
Calcium-rich additions
Durability, geopolymer concrete
Metakaolin

1. Introduction

Geopolymers have shown their potential as promising innovative materials for replacing Portland cement, which remains the world's most widely used binder for construction materials [1]. While they are less polluting and often described as more durable than Portland cement-based materials, the challenges associated with the production

of geopolymers are partly related to the wide range of raw materials eligible for geopolymerization [2,3].

Any amorphous aluminosilicate (material rich in silica and alumina) is eligible for geopolymerization. The difficulty lies in the fact that, depending on the proportions of chemical constituents such as CaO in the precursor and the composition of the activating solution, the outcome can be very different. For example, class F fly ash reacts

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differently compared to class C fly ash during geopolymerization. In terms of reactivity and enhancement of physico-mechanical properties, the former are closer to calcined kaolin clays, while class C fly ash is closer to blast furnace slag [4].

While it is preferable to use a calcium-rich precursor in the production of geopolymers, due to their advantages in terms of reactivity and consequently better mechanical performance [5], the availability of different raw materials in different parts of the world is driving researchers to improve the reactivity of amorphous aluminosilicates, whatever their chemical composition. The most common way of achieving this is to make additions designed to correct the chemical composition of the precursor to some extent.

Approaches such as combinations of class C fly ash with class F fly ash, class F fly ash with blast furnace slag, calcined kaolin clays (Metakaolin) with calcium-rich compounds such as slag, lime or Portland cement are common [4,6].

Metakaolin, which is available in the form of kaolin clay in many parts of the world, is of particular interest to developing countries, unlike blast furnace slag or fly ash, which are industrial wastes of limited availability in less industrialized regions of the globe. As a result, given the growing interest in geopolymers in developed countries due to the global ecological upsurge of recent years, most recent scientific articles on geopolymers in the literature focus on fly ash-type aluminosilicates and blast furnace slag, leaving little attention to metakaolin [7–9].

Some studies have described processes for manufacturing MK-based geopolymers activated by sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide and reached the conclusion that the reactivities and mechanical performance of MK-based geopolymers can be affected by the type of activating solution employed. In the case of MK substitution by fly ash, the use of NaOH is found to be more effective than KOH [10]. When no calcium-rich materials are added, these studies have shown that the mechanical results obtained without thermal curing are relatively low in most cases. Although the introduction of calcium-rich materials improves mechanical performance, its impact on durability is still questionable.

In fact, based on the composition of geopolymer, its durability can be affected by certain stresses in the environment in which it is exposed. The durability of a material reflects its ability to withstand various stresses (chemical, physical, mechanical) over time, while retaining its physical-mechanical and aesthetic integrity.

Generally, for geopolymers, resistance to carbonation, resistance to abrasion, resistance to high temperatures, resistance to acid attack and capillary absorption are essentially the parameters evaluated in most studies intended to assess their durability [11–16].

These various tests are designed to simulate, in accelerated mode, the real-life exposure conditions of these materials, which include alternating dry and rainy seasons; freezing and thawing; abrasion due to the effect of dusty winds in contact with the materials; fires; and marine environments reputed for their high concentration of chloride ions. These data are crucial for establishing calculation standards for estimating the lifespan of engineering structures made of these geopolymer materials. The methodology used to assess these durability indicators is diverse and varied.

The ability of a material to absorb water by capillarity, without the application of any external pressure, is directly related to the size of the material, the shape of the pores and the way in which they are interconnected. This test measures the rate of water absorption by capillary suction of concrete specimens with a single surface in contact with water. The test is conducted at a temperature of 20 °C, avoiding evaporation, on previously dried specimens. They are immersed to a maximum height of 1–2 cm, and at different time intervals over a 24-hour period, the samples are removed from the container, wiped clean with a damp sponge, weighed and returned to the container.

The resistance to wetting-drying cycles, which typifies the alternation of dry and rainy seasons, has been studied by various authors, such as Aygörmüş *et al.* [17] whose work focused on metakaolin-based

geopolymer concretes. The cycles consist of drying the samples at 65 °C for 24 hours, followed by immersion in water at room temperature for 24 hours. After 5, 15 and 25 cycles, parameters such as compressive strength, ultrasonic pulse velocity and mass variations were evaluated. Results showed that after 25 wet-dry cycles, residual compressive strength and ultrasonic pulse velocity were higher than initial values. This suggests that, despite repeated wetting and drying cycles, the concrete samples improved their compressive strength and retained their structural integrity. However, the authors observed a deterioration in the flexural strength of the different concrete formulations attributable to the appearance of microcracks in the concrete matrix.

Similarly to the previous authors, Batista *et al.* evaluated the effect of 10 wetting-drying cycles consisting of drying at 40 °C for two days followed by an immersion in water at 22 °C. Under these conditions, geopolymer concretes recorded a reduction in flexural strength of around 27 % [18].

These results indicate that wetting-drying has a significant impact on the properties of metakaolin-based geopolymer concretes and should be considered when designing full-scale structures.

When concretes are exposed to chemical agents which can interact with the reaction products forming their matrix, their durability can be affected. Acid attack is often encountered in environments where the first rains are acidic, or in chemical storage facilities in the chemical industry. In the literature, the determination of durability indicators related to acid attack is performed using specific acids such as hydrochloric acid, sulfuric acid, nitric acid and others. However, these acids do not have the same effects on geopolymer materials. In some studies, sulfuric acid has shown to be more damaging to geopolymer materials than hydrochloric acid, due to its diacidic nature. Authors have observed more pronounced degradation of metakaolin-based geopolymers immersed for 12 months in 10 % sulfuric acid solution than those immersed in 10 % hydrochloric acid [19].

Work by Abhilash *et al.* has shown that when exposed to sulfuric and hydrochloric acid solutions at 2 % concentration, geopolymer concretes show greater resistance to acid attack than Portland cement hydraulic concretes [20].

Generally, the more calcium a geopolymer material contains, the less resistant it is to chemical attack such as acids environments specifically. Authors evaluated the effect of Portland cement addition on the stability of geopolymer concrete against acid attack by immersing the concrete in a pH 1 sulfuric acid solution for 90 days. They concluded that geopolymer concrete becomes more prone to surface erosion, and the degradation of its mechanical strength becomes greater as the rate of Portland cement addition increases. Although the incorporation of Portland cement improves the strength of geopolymer when it is not exposed to sulfuric acid, the reaction products they form are highly sensitive to sulfuric acid, and this sensitivity increases as the amount of cement increases [21].

Davidovits' work also showed that materials based on Portland cement, slag or calcium aluminates, all of which have high calcium content in common, were less resistant to acid attack (HCl or H₂SO₄) than geopolymers known for their low calcium concentration [22]. More generally, some author proposed a mapping between durability factors and the durability characteristics and reached the conclusion that the type of aluminosilicate and the calcium content of the precursor could play a key role in the overall durability properties of the geopolymer material [2].

Some authors observed that the degradation of geopolymer concretes under 5 % sulfuric acid attack may be related to the destruction of Si-O-Al in the geopolymer matrix by the leaching of aluminum in the Si-O-Al network as they observed a reduction of Al/Si atomic ratio after the acid attack [5].

Recent research has examined the impact of various calcium-rich products, including CCR, Slacked lime, Quicklime, and Portland cement, on the physico-mechanical characteristics of MK-based geopolymer concrete cured at ambient temperature. The findings indicate

that the enhancement of physico-mechanical properties varies for each calcium-rich product. Consequently, the optimal quantity of calcium-rich product necessary for effective geopolymerization at ambient temperature differs for each product, as do the thermochemical and microstructural characteristics. These variations in reactivity and reaction products may result in distinct behaviors in terms of durability [23].

The present study aims to evaluate the durability of geopolymer concretes formulated at room temperature from calcined clay and activated with 12 M sodium hydroxide, to enrich the database on the durability of geopolymer materials cured at room temperature. In order to improve room-temperature curing, part of the calcined clay was substituted by calcium-rich materials such as CCR, slaked lime, quicklime and Portland cement. In particular, the study investigated the resistance of geopolymer concrete to wetting-drying cycles, acid attack and their capillary absorption.

2. Materials and experimental methods

2.1. Materials

2.1.1. Aluminosilicate Materials

The clay used was obtained from Saaba (12°22'44.9''N; 1°24'38''W), a locality in the city of Ouagadougou. It was dried, crushed, sieved and then calcined at 700 °C for 3 hours. The calcination rate is 10 °C/min up to 700 °C and kept constant for 3 hours. The metakaolin obtained from the calcination process is predominantly composed of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ at a cumulative content of 96.2 % (Table 1). Clay's calcination is essentially characterized by dehydroxylation and reorganization of Si-O-T bonds (T = Si or Al) within the material. These transformations are detected in the infrared analysis (Fig. 1) by the disappearance of peaks around 3600 cm⁻¹ (H-O-H bonds) and a rearrangement of peaks around 1060 cm⁻¹ (Si-O-T) and 798 cm⁻¹ (Si-O-Al). XRD analysis (Fig. 2) of the raw and calcined clays shows a disappearance of kaolinite peaks marking the transformation of kaolinite clay into metakaolin. TGA analyses carried out on raw clay and calcined clay also show the transformation of kaolinite peaks marked by the absence of humps between 450 °C and 750 °C on calcined clay. (Figs. 3 and 4)

2.1.2. Calcic materials

- ❖ The Calcium carbide residue (CCR) used is an industrial waste from a local company specializing in the production of acetylene. Once collected, CCR appears in the form of more or less compact lumps. It is coarsely ground with a hammer, dried in the sun, crushed and sieved with an 80 µm sieve, then stored in containers protected from any contamination. The chemical composition of the materials presented in Table 1 shows that the CCR contains a high proportion of CaO (over 66 %).

Table 1
Chemical composition of MK, CCR, QLM, SLM, and OPC.

Oxides (% wt)	MK	CCR	QLM	SLM	OPC
SiO ₂	54.3	3.90	0.27	0.38	22.8
CaO	0.07	60.1	75.5	74.8	54.4
Al ₂ O ₃	42.7	1.72	0.08	0.09	6.64
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.61	0.42	0.03	0.05	4.57
K ₂ O	0.15	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.54
Na ₂ O	0.07	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.53
MgO	0.05	0.17	0.27	0.27	3.10
Mn ₂ O ₃	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08
TiO ₂	0.19	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.41
F	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.12
SO ₃	0.00	0.28	0.03	0.03	2.42
P ₂ O ₅	0.05	0.02	0.12	0.14	0.45
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02
LOI	1.89	33.3	23.6	24.1	3.86

Fig. 1. FTIR analysis of raw clay, MK, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

Fig. 2. XRD analysis of raw clay, MK, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC. k: kaolinite; Q: quartz Silicon oxide SiO₂ α-SiO₂; P: portlandite Ca(OH)₂ syn; C: calcite CaCO₃; G: gypsum CaSO₄(H₂O)₂; An: anorthite CaAl₂Si₂O₈ ordered; Al: alite Ca₃SiO₅; Do: dolomite CaMgO₇₇FeO₂₃(CO₃)₂.

Fig. 3. Thermogravimetric analysis: TG curves of Raw clay, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

- ❖ QLM (quicklime) comes from the local market, where it is commonly used for some paint coats in residential buildings. It is supplied in the form of whitish granules of varying sizes (between 10 and 50 mm in diameter) in 20-kilogram plastic boxes, which are kept dry. These granules are first broken by a metal hammer into small pieces that can be fed into the RETSCH_RS_200 electric planetary disc mill

Fig. 4. Thermogravimetric analysis: DTG curves of Raw clay, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

(grinding is carried out at 700 rpm for 2 minutes). The powder obtained is then sieved at 80 μm and stored in closed containers, away from any contamination.

- ❖ SLM (Slacked or hydrated lime) is obtained by the complete hydration of QLM. The hydration process consists of introducing water onto the quicklime granules until no more exothermic reaction is released. It is then left in water for 24 hours to ensure complete hydration of the quicklime particles. The collected paste is then oven-dried at 105 °C to remove the excess moisture. It is then ground in a planetary disc mill at 700 rpm for 2 minutes. The collected powder is then sieved at 80 μm and stored in containers protected from any contamination.
- ❖ The OPC cement used is a CEM-II/B-M (P-L) 42.5 N corresponding to the 42.5 MPa strength class, with ordinary short-term strength. It contains a mixture of limestone and natural pozzolan and its chemical composition (Table 1) reveals that it is mainly composed of CaO (54.4 %) and SiO₂ (22.8 %). While Type I Portland cement can achieve superior mechanical performance, its availability in the study area is limited to specific projects. The present study made use of Type II Portland cement, given its widespread availability and use in local industry, to favor the practical applicability of the proposed concrete formulation. The findings can be more directly translated into real-world construction practices by utilizing the more readily available Type II cement. Furthermore, unlike type I cements, type II cements contain a significant amount of SiO₂ (22.8 %), which can contribute to the geopolymerisation process.

XRD analysis reveals that CCR is rich in Portlandite and Calcite, while SLM is essentially composed of Portlandite with a few traces of Calcite. QLM is mainly composed of Calcium oxide with barely visible traces of portlandite and calcite. The XRD analysis of Portland cement reveals that it consists mainly of Alite (C₃S) with traces of Gypsum, Dolomite, Calcite and Anorthite. The 3 % MgO content in the cement (Table 1) is therefore linked to the dolomite detected by the XRD analyses. The relatively high losses on ignition of CCR, QLM and SLM (33.3 %, 23.6 % and 24.1 % respectively) are attributed to portlandite dehydration (between 360 °C and 525 °C) and calcite decomposition (between 600 °C and 875 °C), as shown by TGA/DTG results. These thermogravimetric analyses also show that CCR contains relatively high amount of calcite when compared to other calcium-rich materials.

2.1.3. Activation solution

A 12 M sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution was used as the activator. This solution was prepared by dissolving 99 % pure NaOH pellets in distilled water 24 hours prior to use. This concentration has been widely used in previous studies and had been found to be effective for the

activation of MK-based geopolymers [24].

2.1.4. Aggregates

The sand and granitic gravel were purchased locally in the city of Ouagadougou. The river sand and gravel come mainly from local sites. The aggregates have particle sizes in the ranges of 0–5 mm and 5–10 mm, respectively, for sand and gravel (Fig. 5). They were washed and dried at 105 °C in an oven for 24 hours and stored in a container to avoid any contamination. The granulometric analysis shows that the sand has a well-distributed particle size with a fineness modulus of 2.28 and HAZEN uniformity coefficient (Cu) of 3.33, which makes it particularly suitable to produce concrete, while gravel has a uniform particle distribution (Cu = 1.43) which is less than 2, meaning that its particle size is uniform.

2.2. Experimental methods

2.2.1. Concrete formulations, casting, and curing

The composition of the geopolymer concrete is presented in Table 3. The formulation was inspired by literature, notably that of Cao *et al.*, 2018a. The reference formulation is a geopolymer concrete whose binder's precursor is solely composed of metakaolin powder (calcined clay) activated with the 12 M NaOH solution; and is noted 100 % MK. Subsequently, part of the metakaolin is substituted by the calcium-rich material (CCR; QLM; SLM and OPC) at a content of 5 % per stage until optimum strength is reached. Some previous studies have shown that the optimum substitution percentage for calcium compounds is around 15–30 % for certain calcium-rich materials [25,26].

The amount of activating solution is kept constant, though in such a way as to ensure good workability of the concrete, while taking care not to introduce excessive water into the concrete. In this study, the ratio (MK + Ca. Material)/NaOH is kept constant at 0.5 for all concretes to ensure good workability without compromising their performances.

Concrete formulation involved mixing the aggregates (gravel + sand) and the precursor (MK + calcium-rich material). Once the mixture has been homogenized, the sodium hydroxide solution is added gradually, while mixing continues in the mixer.

The molds used are cylindrical (\varnothing 50 mm \times H 100 mm) and prismatic (40 mm \times 40 mm \times 160 mm). They were filled and placed on an electric impact table (twice 60 strokes) to expel the trapped air. The specimens were unmolded 24 hours after setting.

Concrete specimens and pastes were stored at 30 \pm 5 °C and a relative humidity of 50 \pm 10 % then covered in order to limit water loss until the desired curing date. The curing conditions for concrete were designed to closely replicate the ambient temperature regime of the sub-Saharan climate of the study area. This regime, characterized by

Fig. 5. Particle size distribution of aggregates.

Table 2
Physical properties of MK, CCR, QLM, SLM and OPC.

Method	BLAINE	Helium pycnometer	Laser granulometry		
	Specific Surface area (cm ² /g)	Specific density (g/cm ³)	D10 (μm)	D50 (μm)	D90 (μm)
Materials					
MK	18,409	2.67	2.00	10.93	38.71
CCR	8756	2.42	2.53	12.65	39.29
SLM	14,634	2.27	1.78	10.45	28.59
QLM	25,933	2.32	1.51	6.57	18.55
OPC	3484	3.10	2.29	13.57	36.29

Table 3
Mix design of the geopolymer concretes.

Material (kg/m ³)	Calcium product [CCR; OPC; QLM; SLM] content (%)				
	0	5	10	15	20
MK	350	332.5	315	298	280
Ca product	0	17.5	35	53	70
NaOH pellets	126	126	126	126	126
Water	229	229	229	229	229
Sand	723	723	723	723	723
Gravel	958	958	958	958	958

average monthly temperatures around 30°C, has been adopted in previous studies [27,28]. The nomenclature of the concrete is related to the nature and the percentage of the calcium-rich product that it contains. For example, the concrete containing 15 % of the metakaolin substituted by quick lime was called 15QLM and the concrete noted 25CCR corresponds to the one in which 25 % of the total mass of metakaolin is replaced by CCR.

2.2.2. Characterization methods

The effect of wetting-drying cycles was assessed by measuring the residual mechanical strength of prismatic concrete specimens that had undergone these cycles. A cycle consists of a succession of wetting by total immersion for 24 h at 20 °C and drying for 24 h at 50 °C. After each cycle, mass changes were recorded. A total of 10 cycles are performed before evaluating residual flexural and compressive strengths, and variations in ultrasonic pulse velocity in concrete specimens.

The acid attack resistance of the concrete specimens was tested with two types of acid: sulfuric acid and hydrochloric acid. Mass losses, water accessible porosity and residual compressive strengths of concrete specimens after total immersion in acid solutions were evaluated on cylindrical samples by considering the residual diameter. After curing, the cylindrical samples were fully immersed in sulfuric acid and hydrochloric acid solutions of 0.5 % and 1 % volumetric concentration respectively, maintaining a pH of 1 ± 0.5 throughout the test period. Mass loss and porosity variation were evaluated at 7, 14 and 28 days of immersion, as were residual compressive strengths.

The capillary test was conducted at 20 °C, avoiding evaporation, on previously dried specimens. Concretes samples are immersed to a maximum height of 1–2 cm. At different time intervals up to 24-hour period, the samples were removed from the container, wiped clean with a damp sponge, weighed and returned to the container. The capillary absorption coefficient is defined by the equation below, where Ca is the capillary absorption coefficient (kg/m²), M_t is the mass of the test specimen at a given time (kg), M_i is the initial mass of the test specimen (kg) and A is the cross-sectional area of the tested specimen (m²).

$$Ca = \frac{M_t - M_i}{A} \quad (1)$$

Porosity is an important parameter influencing the durability and mechanical properties of concrete. It is defined as the ratio between the

volume of voids and the apparent volume of the material. Water-accessible porosity is determined in accordance with standard NF P 18–459 of august 2022. All operations were performed at 20 °C, except for drying, which was performed at 105 °C. The specimens were immersed in water for 48 h, then the hydrostatic in water and in-air masses were determined after removal, then the dry mass was determined after drying to constant mass. From these operations, we can also determine the apparent density of the specimens. The below relationships can be used to determine the water-accessible porosity (ε) of different concretes where: M_w corresponds to the mass of the sample weighed in water, M_{air} corresponds to its initial mass weighed in air and M_d corresponds to the mass of the dried concrete sample.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{M_{air} - M_d}{M_{air} - M_w} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The Pundit test is a non-destructive test that assesses the properties of concrete by measuring the speed of ultrasound within the concrete using an ultrasonic pulse velocity tester. The concrete specimen is placed between two probes (one transmitting and one receiving), and the propagation time is displayed by the acquisition unit after the device has been switched on. Velocity (v) is expressed as the ratio of distance to time of propagation.

After the desired curing and/or exposure date, the mechanical properties were assessed through compressive strength determination using a PROETTI hydro-electric press, which has a capacity of 300 kN with a load rate of 0.98 kN/s until failure. For each mix design, the recorded value was an average of 3 measurements. The compressive strength [MPa], is the ratio of the load at failure [N], and the cross-section area [mm²] of the specimen.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Physical properties of geopolymer concretes

3.1.1. Evolution of the apparent density and accessible porosity by water

Fig. 6 shows the porosity and bulk density of geopolymer concretes after 90 days of curing. Analysis of these results shows that the concretes have bulk densities ranging from 2096 to 2149 kg/m³. The variation observed on these different formulations is of the order of 2.5 %, indicating that the various additions of calcium-rich materials have no significant effect on the apparent density of the concretes after 90 days of curing. Compared with ordinary hydraulic concrete, which has an apparent density of around 2450 kg/m³, these concretes are relatively less dense (-12 %), providing an advantage in reducing the weight of the structures in which they are to be used as observed in previous studies [29].

Furthermore, this figure reveals that these concretes have an average porosity of 14.5 %. However, maximum porosity was observed on the 100MK reference concrete, with a measured value of 16.1 %. This indicates that the addition of calcium-rich materials to geopolymer concretes makes them less porous, due to the formation of new reaction products. This observation is in line with similar studies showing that the addition of calcium-rich materials to a geopolymer led to the formation of new reaction products that tend to modify the percolation paths within these materials, making them less sensitive to water absorption. However, the authors note that when these calcium additions become too important, a slight increase in porosity can be observed due to a decrease in the effectiveness of geopolymerization reactions caused by an unbalanced ratio linked to the decrease in aluminosilicate in the reaction medium [30,36].

Studies have also reported water-accessible porosity and bulk density values of 16 % and 2170 kg/m³ respectively for a geopolymer concrete based on metakaolin and blast furnace slag [31]. Other authors have observed that the porosity of geopolymer concretes at 90 days of curing ranged from 13 % to 6.2 % when the content of replacement of aluminosilicate by Portland cement increased from 0 % to 30 % [30].

Fig. 6. Apparent density and accessible porosity by water of geopolymer concretes.

3.1.2. Water absorption

Fig. 7, Fig. 8 and Table 4 presents the results of capillary absorption of the geopolymer concretes. The 100MK geopolymer concrete has the highest capillary absorption capacity and the highest sorptivity, i.e. the highest absorption rate of all formulations. This concrete already reaches saturation after 4 hours of capillary absorption.

When MK is replaced by CCR, the sorptivity of the material is reduced from $6.71 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-0.5}$ to values between 4.17 and $5.47 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-0.5}$, corresponding to an improvement in sorptivity of around 18.5–37.8 %. Although the substitution of MK by CCR reduces the overall capillary water absorption of geopolymer concretes, the results indicate that a substitution of more than 15 % would be inadvisable due to the increase in sorptivity observed when the substitution rate of MK by CCR passes 20 %. Consequently, when CCR is used as a substitute for MK, a substitution rate of around 15 % would present optimal characteristics in terms of capillary absorption.

Still, even at this rate, the results show saturation as early as 8 hours of absorption for 15CCR concrete, in contrast to the results obtained with other calcium-rich products such as QLM, SLM and OPC, which have relatively lower capillary absorption and sorptivity coefficients and

Fig. 8. Capillary water absorption of concretes containing Quick lime (QLM) and Calcium carbide residue (CCR).

Fig. 7. Capillary water absorption of concretes containing Slacked lime (SLM) and Portland cement (OPC).

Table 4
Coefficient of capillary water absorption and sorptivity of geopolymer concretes.

Mix Design	Coefficient of capillary absorption (kg/m^2)		Sorptivity ($1\text{--}24 \text{ hours}$) $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-0.5}$
	1 hour	24 hours	
100MK	7.39	16.14	6.71
05QLM	2.75	10.07	1.84
10QLM	2.20	9.73	1.90
15QLM	1.72	8.65	1.75
05CCR	6.71	13.66	5.47
10CCR	6.41	14.02	5.40
15CCR	5.15	14.08	4.17
20CCR	6.17	14.49	4.86
05SLM	2.83	9.47	1.74
10SLM	2.42	8.08	1.44
15SLM	2.24	7.84	1.42
10OPC	3.47	10.86	1.88
15OPC	3.05	10.44	1.83

therefore better durability in terms of their sorptivity.

When MK is replaced by QLM, the sorptivity of the material is reduced from $6.71 \text{ kg.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-0.5}$ to values between 1.75 and $1.9 \text{ kg.m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-0.5}$, corresponding to an improvement in sorptivity of the order of 71.6–73.9 %. The substitute of MK by SLM hydrated lime and Portland cement leads to similar results, with sorptivity improvements in the order of 74–78.8 % and 72–72.7 % respectively. Remarkably, all concretes containing one of these three calcium-rich products showed no saturation even 24 hours after the start of measurements.

Capillary absorption is closely linked to pore connectivity within the material matrix. In other words, the more interconnected the pores, the higher the sorptivity. The results show that the substitution of metakaolin by CaO-rich elements creates a discontinuity between the different pores present in concrete, resulting in lower capillary absorption and lower sorptivity. These improvements could be associated with the formation of new reaction products related to these calcium-rich products. Overall, these results corroborate the microstructural observations made on the binder of these geopolymer concretes. Indeed, the reference concrete 100MK, exhibiting the highest capillary water absorption capacity, had a microstructure primarily composed of well-crystallized X and A zeolites and a porous matrix. However, when calcium-based products such as CCR, QLM, SLM or OPC were used as partial replacements for metakaolin, the authors noted the formation of

new reaction products such as heulandite and calcium carbonates. Furthermore, when these calcium-based products were employed, the authors demonstrated that the amorphous sodium-aluminosilicate hydrate (N-A-S-H) gels initially present in the binder structure of the 100MK reference concrete underwent a transformation by incorporating calcium from the calcium-rich product, gradually evolving into low-calcium sodium-aluminosilicate hydrates (low-Ca C-(N)-A-S-H) gel [36]. These new reaction products could alter percolation pathways by creating discontinuities in the pores, thus reducing the capillary water absorption capacity of these materials, as observed in this study.

Sore *et al.* came to similar conclusions. The authors observed that the incorporation of 10–15 % Portland cement in geopolymer concrete cured at room temperature led to a 50 % reduction in sorptivity, from 4.82 to 2.21 and $2.14 \text{ kg.m}^{-2}.\text{h}^{-0.5}$ respectively for 0, 10 and 15 % cement [25]. Similar studies found that the sorptivity measured on geopolymer mortars ranged from $17 \text{ }\mu\text{m.s}^{-0.5}$ to $39 \text{ }\mu\text{m.s}^{-0.5}$ when the activator was 12 M NaOH [32].

Mehta *et al.* observed similar results on geopolymer concretes with sorptivity values between 2.69 and $3.83 \text{ }\mu\text{m.s}^{-0.5}$ [30]. Deb observed a sorptivity coefficient between 1.2 and $3.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m.s}^{-0.5}$ for geopolymer mortars cured at room temperature based on fly ash and calcium-rich additions such as slag and Portland cement [33].

Fig. 9. Ultrasonic pulse velocity (a) and flexural strength (b) of geopolymer concretes submitted to 10 wetting-drying cycles.

3.2. Resistance to wetting-drying cycles

3.2.1. Evolution of the ultrasonic pulse velocity

Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 presents the results of ultrasonic pulse velocity, flexural strength and compressive strength of geopolymer concrete after 10 cycles of wetting/drying. Initially, the addition of calcium-rich materials to geopolymer concrete results in an increase in ultrasound propagation velocity. In 100MK reference concrete, the initial ultrasonic pulse velocity of 3477 m/s increases to 4549 m/s (+31 %) with the addition of 5 % quicklime. The same trend is observed with the addition of other calcium-rich products such as CCR, SLM and OPC. As observed during the capillary test, these calcic materials consequently lead to a densification of the geopolymer matrix, which in turn can improve the mechanical performance of the concretes.

Furthermore, the addition of these calcium-rich products to geopolymer concrete results in an overall change in ultrasonic pulse velocities, when these concretes are exposed to 10 wetting-drying cycles.

While the 100MK reference concrete experiences a densification of its matrix, perceptible by an increase in its velocity from 3477 to 3755 m/s (+8 %) after the wetting and drying cycles, concretes containing a calcium-rich addition experience a decrease in the propagation velocity of ultrasonic waves after the wetting and drying cycles. At the end of the wetting-drying cycle, the speed decreases from 4539 to 3361 (-26 %), from 4079 to 3368 (-17.4 %), from 4167 to 3758 (-9.8 %) and from 3963 to 3590 m/s (-9.4 %) respectively for concretes containing 10 % QLM, CCR, SLM and OPC calcium-rich additions. The same decreasing trend was observed for other contents of substitution of metakaolin by these calcium-rich products. Although the addition of calcium-rich materials results in an overall densification of the geopolymer concrete matrix, these results indicate that geopolymer concretes are sensitive to wetting-drying cycles, with the probable appearance of micro-cracks resulting in lower ultrasonic pulse velocities. Wetting-drying cycles in general, and the drying phase in particular, can lead to shrinkage in the concrete, which in turn can result in the formation of microcracks in the material [34]. Similar results have been obtained with geopolymer materials, where a reduction in ultrasonic pulse velocities has been observed after repeated wetting-drying cycles [35].

3.2.2. Evolution of the flexural and compressive strength

Analysis of flexural strength results tends to corroborate the hypothesis that microcracks appear in concretes following wetting-drying cycles for certain families of concretes.

Concretes containing calcium-rich additions such as QLM, CCR and SLM experience a reduction in flexural strength following wetting-

drying cycles. This is particularly pronounced for concretes incorporating CCR, where a 49 % reduction in flexural strength was observed for 15 CCR concrete, whose initial strength of 5.3 MPa decreased to 2.7 MPa after the wetting-drying cycles. This reduction is like that observed for ultrasonic pulse velocities, and once again tends to confirm the appearance of additional porosity emanating from microcracks following wetting-drying cycles for this family of concrete.

However, another family of concretes displays the opposite behavior to that described above. The 100MK reference concrete showed a 73 % increase in flexural strength from 0.8 to 3.0 MPa. For this concrete, this observation is also in line with the increase in ultrasonic pulse velocities described above, which may be linked to additional geopolymerization during the drying phases at 50 °C. The same trend can also be observed for concretes where OPC substituted metakaolin, with a 43 % and 24 % increase in flexural strength from 3.0 to 4.3 MPa and from 2.5 to 3.2 MPa respectively for 10OPC and 15OPC concretes. However, for this family of calcium-rich products, this increase contradicts the results of the ultrasonic pulse velocity. Similar work has shown that when Portland cement is used to replace aluminosilicate in geopolymers, the improvement in mechanical performance after wetting-drying cycles is linked to the formation of hydration products of cement in contact with water when the entire cement has not been consumed during the geopolymerization reactions.

According to the results obtained, the sensitivity of geopolymer concretes to wetting-drying cycles differs with the type of calcium-rich products used. Portland cement as an additive in geopolymer would improve its flexural and compressive performances after wetting-drying cycles. In contrast, despite a decrease in flexural strength after wetting-drying cycles, all concretes containing calcium-rich products, such as CCR, QLM and SLM, have a final compressive strength higher than the initial flexural strength of the reference concrete before exposure.

Compressive strength resulting from wetting-drying cycles show that, overall, there is an improvement in the compressive strength of all concretes, except for concretes with CCR substitutions exceeding 5 %. More specifically, when metakaolin is substituted by 15 % LME, a significant increase in compressive strength is observed, with a 37 % increase from 24.9 to 39.8 MPa. On the other hand, when metakaolin is replaced by 15 % CCR, compressive strength decreases by around 25 %, from 36.4 to 27.3 MPa. High amount of CCR in MK-based geopolymer concrete could therefore be detrimental to its stability to wetting-drying cycle.

The increase in compressive strength observed on the other concrete is not in contradiction with the decrease in flexural strength after wetting-drying cycles. Indeed, even if additional geopolymerization takes place during the drying phases at 50 °C due to the additional heat

Fig. 10. Compressive strength of concretes submitted to 10 wetting-drying cycles.

resulting in improved compressive strengths, the appearance of microcracks, highlighted by a reduction in ultrasonic pulse velocities, may create preferential flexural fracture paths. As a result, it can be summarized that geopolymer concrete is more affected in flexure than in compression after wetting-drying cycles.

Other studies of geopolymer materials have produced similar results as they reached the conclusion that the compressive strength of geopolymer concrete could increase under efflorescence conditions, but with a decrease in tensile strength due to crystallization pressures caused by carbonate salt deposition in the geopolymer matrix [36,37].

Some researchers have observed that after 56 wetting-drying cycles, geopolymer materials experienced an improvement in compressive strength, while flexural strength decreased [16]. However, when the number of wetting-drying cycles increased to 90, the geopolymer materials tended to suffer more significant damage, resulting in a decrease in both flexural and compressive mechanical performance [17,35]. Elsewhere, some authors have reported that the decrease in mechanical performance after wetting-drying cycles could be attributed to the leaching of alkalinity by water and the loss of cohesion in sodium aluminosilicate hydrate (N-A-S-H) gels [10].

The Fig. 11 presents the correlation between the mechanical properties (compressive and flexural strengths) and the ultrasonic pulse velocity of geopolymer concretes before and after exposure to wetting-drying cycles.

These results show a general decrease in concrete UPV after the wetting-drying cycles, reflecting the appearance of porosity within the concrete matrix. Furthermore, there appears to be a more random distribution of data after the wetting-drying cycles, marked by a lower coefficient of determination of the regression curve ($R^2 = 0.32$) after the wetting-drying cycles, compared with the initial value of 0.52 when compressive strength is correlated to ultrasonic pulse velocity. This dispersive tendency is even more pronounced when flexural and UPV are correlated and can be seen by a lower coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.07$) after wetting-drying cycles. The lack of correlation between

Fig. 11. Effect of wetting-drying cycles: Correlation between compressive strength and ultrasonic pulse velocity (a); Correlation between Flexural strength and ultrasonic pulse velocity (b).

UPV values and flexural strengths would once more suggest the appearance of cracks constituting preferential failure points when concretes are subjected to flexural stresses. Overall, these findings demonstrate that concrete behavior becomes increasingly difficult to predict when subjected to wet-dry cycles.

3.3. Resistance to acid attack

3.3.1. Evolution of the mass loss

Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 present the results of mass losses of geopolymer concretes after 3, 7, 14 and 28 days of immersion in sulfuric and hydrochloric acid solution respectively (pH of 1 ± 0.5). Table 5 summarizes the linear correlation factor between the mass loss (%) and the immersion time (days^{0.5}) during acid attack (Fig. 14)

These results indicate that all samples are subjected to mass losses when immersed in acid solutions and these mass losses increase linearly with the square root of immersion time with the coefficients of determination ranging from 0.69 to 0.99. However, the degree of degradation observed in sulfuric acid is more pronounced than in hydrochloric acid as shown by higher slope values (a) in sulfuric acid compared to hydrochloric acid in Table 5. Indeed, after 28 days of immersion, mass losses reach 2.7 % and 1.3 % of the initial mass in sulfuric acid and hydrochloric acid solutions respectively. It should be noted that the 100MK reference concrete shows practically the same level of degradation in the sulfuric acid solution as in the hydrochloric acid solution. For this concrete, mass loss after 28 days' immersion ranges from 1.1 % to 0.9 % in both sulfuric and hydrochloric acid, and thus it remains the concrete that best retains its mass under acid attack.

On the other hand, concretes tend to exhibit greater damage as the calcium-rich product content increases. When the QLM substitution rate increases from 0 % to 15 %, mass losses after 28 days of immersion in sulfuric acid increases from 1.1 % to 2.2 %. The same trend can be observed for concrete containing CCR, where mass loss increases under the same conditions from 1.1 % to 2.5 % when the CCR substitution rate is increased from 0 % to 25 %. Furthermore, among calcium-rich products, concretes containing OPC Portland cement tend to show the highest mass losses.

When concretes are immersed in hydrochloric acid for 28 days, mass losses observed on concretes containing QLM, CCR or SLM show similar levels of degradation. When the substitution rate is increased from 0 % to 15 %, mass loss on concrete samples rises from 0.9 % to 1.1 %.

Concretes containing 10 % and 15 % Portland cement recorded a degradation of 1.3 % of the initial mass. As the degradations observed after immersion in sulfuric acid are relatively lower, it would be more appropriate to extend immersion times to 90 days to better assess long-term degradations.

The observed mass losses are in the same range as those reported by Deb *et al.* who noted a mass loss of geopolymer mortars of around 6 % during a prolonged 90-day immersion in a 3 % sulfuric acid solution [33]. Some studies observed no degradation but, instead, an increase in the mass of geopolymer materials by around 1.5 % after 90 days' prolonged immersion in 10 % sulfuric acid. However, the author employed sodium silicate alongside sodium hydroxide leading to possible different reaction products in the materials [32].

Several investigations has also shown that sulfuric acid is more damaging than hydrochloric acid [19,38]. Indeed, sulfuric acid is known for its ability to decompose $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the matrices of materials containing it. The decomposition of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ produces gypsum which, through its ability to swell, denatures the matrix of materials and leads to their gradual disintegration [33]. Furthermore, portlandite's alkalinity plays an essential role in the stability of certain reaction products, notably those resulting from the hydration of Portland cement. Consequently, its denaturation indirectly leads to the denaturation of these reaction products, whose presence is crucial to the structural integrity of concrete. Recently, it has been demonstrated that the calcium phases contained in geopolymers tend to transform into gypsum after exposure

Fig. 12. Mass loss of geopolymer concrete in sulfuric acid solution (pH of 1 ± 0.5) with square root of time: a): QLM samples; b): CCR samples; c): SLM samples; d): OPC samples.

Fig. 13. Mass loss of geopolymer concrete in hydrochloric acid solution (pH of 1 ± 0.5) with square root of time: a): QLM samples; b): CCR samples; c): SLM samples; d): OPC samples.

to sulfuric acid [39].

3.3.2. Evolution of the compressive strength

Fig. 15 and Fig. 16 present the results of the compressive strengths of geopolymer concrete after 7, 14 and 28 days of immersion in sulfuric and hydrochloric acid respectively. Table 6 summarizes the strength loss of geopolymer in acid attack.

Similarly to the mass losses discussed in the previous section, all concretes gradually reduce strength when the immersion time increases.

In the sulfuric acid solution, the 100MK reference concrete registered -49.6% reduction in compressive strength, from 12.5 to 6.3 MPa after 28 days of immersion. However, this decrease in strength did not occur linearly over this period. In fact, strength losses during the first few days of immersion appear more pronounced. The loss of strength during the

Table 5

Linear correlation factors between the mass loss (Y) and the square root of immersion time (T) during acid attack.

Mix Design	$Y = aT^{0.5} + b$					
	Sulfuric acid			Hydrochloric acid		
	a	b	R ²	a	b	R ²
100MK	0.195	0.077	0.89	0.194	-0.112	0.90
05QLM	0.345	-0.181	0.99	0.207	-0.081	0.82
10QLM	0.391	0.018	0.98	0.241	-0.146	0.94
15QLM	0.414	0.155	0.88	0.255	-0.202	0.91
05CCR	0.489	-0.734	0.96	0.149	-0.070	0.87
10CCR	0.501	-0.736	0.98	0.170	-0.108	0.95
15CCR	0.534	-0.782	0.98	0.186	-0.007	0.87
20CCR	0.660	-1.038	0.99	0.233	-0.059	0.93
05SLM	0.286	0.085	0.85	0.174	0.026	0.87
10SLM	0.260	0.381	0.85	0.160	0.114	0.69
15SLM	0.219	0.595	0.87	0.265	-0.181	0.96
10OPC	0.588	-0.824	0.99	0.343	-0.577	0.97
15OPC	0.728	-1.192	0.99	0.337	-0.527	0.98

first 7 days of immersion is -36.6 %, and only -12.8 % between days 7 and 28. This means that there is probably a period of accelerated degradation, as observed in previous studies [38,40]. This interval could correspond to the time necessary for the degradation to reach the coarse aggregates, i.e. the gravels, after the mortar layer covering these gravels has been eroded away, as shown in Fig. 17. The reference concrete which is plain Metakaolin-based geopolymer concrete is characterized by a very low compressive strength (12.5 MPa) indicating a weak and porous (highest porosity as shown in Fig. 6) matrix vulnerable to chemical attacks such as acids. Furthermore, capillary water absorption results (Figure 7Figure 8) indicated that liquids such as water or acids penetrate faster the reference concrete due to its high porosity and may justify the quick decrease of compressive strength during acid attack. Previous studies have reached similar conclusions. In fact, it has been shown that the more porous the material's matrix, the more susceptible it is to chemical attack, resulting in a reduction in mechanical performance under acid attack [33,41].

When metakaolin is substituted by calcium-rich products in concretes, they experience a gradual decline in mechanical strength following immersion in these acids. However, the loss of strength in acid solution is more pronounced for some concretes. In sulfuric acid solution, the strength of 15CCR concrete drops from 31 to 15.9 MPa, representing a reduction of -48.7 %. A similar degradation occurs when the concrete is immersed in hydrochloric acid solution, where the initial pre-immersion strength of 31 MPa drops to 19.9 MPa (-35.8 %). Like in the case of 100MK reference concrete, these degradations are not linear. In fact, the degradation accelerates during the first 7 days of immersion (-27.4 %), compared with the degradation observed between the 7th and 14th days of immersion (-17 %) or between the 14th and 28th days of immersion (-4 %) in sulfuric acid solution. The other CCR-containing formulations also appear to suffer significant deterioration in strength in sulfuric acid solution, with a reduction in strength of between 29.6 % and 46.8 % when the substitution rate varies between 5 % and 20 %. As a result, the overall conclusion is that geopolymer concrete containing CCR retains its initial strength better in acidic conditions when the CCR content is reduced. This finding is in line with observations made in similar studies. Indeed, calcium-rich products that likely contain Ca(OH)₂ are more prone to degrade rapidly in an acid environment [42]. The samples of concrete containing quicklime suffer less from strength loss after immersion in an acid medium than concretes containing other calcium-rich additions. The strength loss after 28 days immersion in sulfuric acid solution for concretes containing quicklime ranged from 10.7 % to 22 %. In hydrochloric acid, strength losses ranged from 8.9 % to 17.7 % after 28 days immersion. Overall, after 28 days of acid attack, all QLM-containing concretes have compressive strengths superior to 20 MPa, satisfying the mechanical dimensioning requirements of most

current structures.

These findings align with previous microstructural investigations of the authors related to the influence of calcium-rich additions on the microstructural characteristics of ambient-cured MK-based geopolymer concretes. The authors identified distinctive hexagonal plate-like structures resembling portlandite within the binder matrix of geopolymer concretes incorporating calcium-based components such as CCR, SLM, and OPC. These platelets may exhibit a particular susceptibility to acidic environments, like portlandite. This potential vulnerability could explain the enhanced sensitivity to acidic conditions observed in CCR, SLM, and OPC-based geopolymer concretes compared to their QLM counterpart.

Indeed, the binder matrix of geopolymer concretes containing CCR, SLM, and OPC displayed a profusion of these portlandite-like platelets, in contrast to the QLM concrete, which exhibited no such features. Conversely, the QLM concrete matrix contained filamentous inclusions with lower calcium content compared to the hexagonal platelets. While CCR-based concretes also displayed these portlandite-like structures, their abundance was relatively higher than in SLM and OPC-based concretes [23].

Furthermore, the reduction in mechanical strength after exposure to acid attack may be justified by the degradation of unreacted calcium-rich material in the microstructure of the geopolymer matrix. As illustrated in Fig. 14, SEM analysis of the 15CCR paste revealed an inhomogeneous microstructure characterized by unreacted CCR particles. The high portlandite content of the calcium-rich materials such as CCR (Fig. 2) renders it susceptible to acid attack and could lead to increased porosity within the concrete matrix and potential degradation of mechanical properties when all the calcium-rich material introduced didn't completely react within the geopolymer matrix.

These observations suggest that the acid resistance of geopolymer concretes is influenced by their microstructure, particularly the presence of portlandite-like phases. Concretes containing calcium-rich products with a higher propensity to form portlandite are more susceptible to acidic environments especially sulfuric acid environments. The suggested correlation between the acid susceptibility of geopolymer concretes and the presence of portlandite-like phases in their microstructure underscores the importance of selecting appropriate calcium-based additives with the exposure environment. In highly sulfuric environments, QLM emerges as a more promising candidate than SLM, CCR, or OPC. For environments rich in hydrochloric acid, although concretes generally exhibit higher resistance than in sulfuric acid, addition content should be limited to 15 % for CCR and 10 % for QLM, SLM, and OPC in order to achieve optimal performances.

3.4. Conclusions and perspectives

The aim of this study was to evaluate the durability of Metakaolin-based geopolymer concretes under ambient-temperature curing promoted by the addition of calcium-rich products. The findings show that:

- The addition of calcium-rich products to MK-based geopolymer concrete improves its initial mechanical properties under room-temperature curing conditions.
- The addition of calcium-rich products to concrete has a negligible effect on its water-accessible porosity, which averages around 14.5 %.
- The addition of calcium-rich products to geopolymer concretes has a negligible effect on their apparent density, which has an average value of 2113 kg/m³.
- The addition of calcium-rich products densifies the concrete matrix, reducing its capillary water absorption capacity through the formation of new reaction products that create pore discontinuities and consequently reduce its sorptivity by over 70 %.
- CCR improves concrete sorptivity only slightly, and all concretes containing CCR have a sorptivity 2 times higher than concretes

Fig. 14. SEM analyses of 15 CCR paste after 90 curing days before exposure to acid attack.

containing other calcium-rich products, resulting in saturation of CCR-containing concrete samples after 8 hours of immersion.

- Under wetting-drying conditions, concretes show an overall improvement in compressive strength due to additional geopolymerization during the drying phases.
- After repeated wetting and drying cycles, concretes are more affected in bending than in compression.
- After 28 days of immersion in 0.5 % sulfuric acid and 1 % hydrochloric acid, the degradation observed in the sulfuric acid solution is greater than in hydrochloric acid.
- The acid resistance of geopolymer concretes is influenced by their microstructure, particularly the presence of portlandite-like phases:

Concretes containing calcium-rich product with a higher propensity to form portlandite are more susceptible to acidic environments especially sulfuric acid environment.

- Concrete containing quicklime exhibits the best overall durability properties and retains a compressive strength higher than 20 MPa after 28 of immersion in 0.5 % sulfuric acid or 1 % hydrochloric acid.

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Fig. 15. Compressive strength of geopolymer concrete after exposure to H₂SO₄ acid solution. (pH of 1 ± 0.5).

Fig. 16. Compressive strength of geopolymer concrete after exposure to HCl acid solution. (pH of 1 ± 0.5).

Table 6

Strength loss of geopolymer concretes exposed to acid attack.

Mix Design	Sulfuric acid			Hydrochloric acid		
	7 days	14 days	28 days	7 days	14 days	28 days
100MK	-36.9	-40.8	-49.6	-24.0	-11.2	-16.8
05QLM	+ 0.1	-8.2	-22	-8.5	-14.8	-17.7
10QLM	-6.0	-5.0	-10.7	-7.0	-9.0	-9.7
15QLM	-0.0	-3.9	-14.0	-5.8	-4.7	-8.9
05CCR	-17.0	-22.8	-32.5	-6.3	-8.3	-26.7
10CCR	-27.4	-32.4	-34.0	-0.8	-20.3	-27.4
15CCR	-27.4	-44.5	-48.7	-9.7	-28.7	-35.8
20CCR	-42.9	-40.8	-46.8	-33.0	-39.1	-40.3
05SLM	-2.3	-11.2	-12.1	+ 6.0	+ 6.0	-5.6
10SLM	-1.8	-34.1	-23.2	-1.4	-1.8	-19.5
15SLM	+ 2.0	-15.3	-30.0	-2.0	-8.9	-15.8
10OPC	-22.0	-17.6	-36.7	-10.9	-22.8	-32.3
15OPC	-16.3	-18.7	-30.3	-2.7	-22.4	-30.6

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Adufu Yawo Daniel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Escadeillas Gilles:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sore Seick Omar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Nshimiyimana Philbert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Ahouandjinou Kpedétin David:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Messan Adamah:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Daniel Adufu reports financial support was provided by World Bank. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have

Fig. 17. Visual aspect of 10QLM specimen after exposure to sulfuric acid: a) initial aspect b) 14 day exposure; c) 28 day exposure.

appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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